

It Is Far From Certain We Live in a Simulation

Andrew Jackson ^{1,2}

¹*School of Informatics, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, EH8 9AB, United Kingdom*

²*Department of Physics, University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL, United Kingdom*

(Dated: April 2, 2026)

The claim that we are almost certainly living in a simulation is examined through the construction of a model wherein: a non-negligible fraction of civilizations reach technological sophistication to be able to run ancestor simulations, a non-negligible fraction of civilizations that can run ancestor simulations do, and the probability of living in a simulation is non-negligibly less than one.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the idea that we live in a simulation has become increasingly prominent, often with the additional opinion that this is a certainty: legions of celebrities line up to inform us *with certainty* that above our reality there exists another that – in some sense – is “more real” than ours.

The reasoning behind this – seemingly extremely deep – idea is *not* deeply philosophical or hard to understand. It originates in the seminal work of Nick Bostrom’s 2003 paper, “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?” [1], the key argument of which is the following trilemma:

At least one of the following propositions must be true:

1. Almost no civilization reaches a level of technological maturity capable of running ancestor simulations
2. Almost no civilization capable of running ancestor simulations chooses to do so
3. We are almost certainly living in a simulation

In the years following Bostrom’s publication, the theory transitioned from a niche philosophical speculation to a cultural touchstone but – at least in popular culture – lost its trilemma form, instead regularly being stated as we “*almost certainly*” live in a simulation.

Recent scientific engagement with simulation theory, on the other hand, has focused on identifying empirical signatures that might distinguish a simulated universe from a “base”

physical reality [2–4]. In the hope that we might identify which of the two our universe is.

These arguments will not be my focus herein. In fact, my considerations will not rely on any physical inspection of our universe at all. Instead, I present a feasible model that contradicts the trilemma.

The model constructed herein is presented for the purpose of arguing positively that we do *not* live in a simulation; instead, I present a model of worlds and simulations they perform wherein none of the options in the trilemma above are true. This then argues *less for* us not living in and more *against* the certainty that we do.

This paper continues, from here, with a discussion of the assumptions that form the models’ bases – in Sec. II. It then – in Sec. III – gives a simplified model before – in Sec. IV – presenting the full, more complex, model. Finally, in Sec. VI, it draws final conclusions.

II. ASSUMPTIONS

The first step in building any model is establishing the assumptions and notation it will be built on. The first of these is a simplification of the considerations around the probabilities of simulations being built. It is convenient to merge the probabilities that a given civilization reaches the level of technical maturity to be capable of running an ancestor simulation, that they are interested in running an ancestor simulation, and that they actually *do* run an ancestor simulation into a single probability. I.e., instead of considering $\mathbb{P}[\text{Can run simulations}]$ and $\mathbb{P}[\text{Wants to run simulations} \mid \text{Can run simulations}]$ individually, I consider just:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{P}[\text{Wants to run simulations} \mid \text{Can run simulations}] \mathbb{P}[\text{Can run simulations}] \\ &= \mathbb{P}[\text{Can run simulations and wants to run simulations}] = \mathbb{P}[\text{Does run simulations}]. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Hence, assuming that both:

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{Wants to run simulations} \mid \text{Can run simulations}] \approx 0 \text{ and } \mathbb{P}[\text{Can run simulations}] \approx 0 \quad (2)$$

implies that:

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{Does run simulations}] \approx 0. \quad (3)$$

This is not an assumption as it is always possible.

Note that as the stated purpose of the models presented

herein is to give a model where none of the options in the trilemma are true. Therefore, I do not need to argue that each choice is *the* correct choice, just that they are a valid and reasonable choice.

A. Poisson Assumption

The Poisson assumption can be expressed as in Assumption 1.

Assumption 1. *For any civilization, the number of simulations a given civilization will create is random with a Poisson distribution (with parameter λ that can be decided later).*

The first step in discussing the assumption herein – in the more complex model – that the number of simulations a given civilization will create is random with a Poisson distribution (with parameter λ) is the definition of Poisson distributions (as in Def. 1).

Definition 1. A discrete random variable, X , has a Poisson distribution with parameter, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$, if the probability that X takes the value $k \in \mathbb{N}^+$ is:

$$\frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}. \quad (4)$$

With Poisson distributions defined, the next natural question is when is a Poisson distribution an appropriate model? It is known that a Poisson distribution is an appropriate model for a random value $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ is if:

1. k is the number of times an event occurs in an interval.
2. The occurrence of one event does not affect the probability of a second event.
3. The average rate at which events occur is independent of any occurrences.
4. Two events cannot occur at exactly the same instant.

These requirements for a Poisson distribution to be appropriate are approximately met in the situation of how many simulations a universe creates as:

1. The interval considered is the duration from the dawn of a civilization to the collapse of that society (including if the simulation is ceased by its simulators). I assume these to be approximately the same in all simulations as they are all based on the same starting parameters and are likely to be simulations of the same thing with the same or similar objectives.
2. It is likely that a universe where multiple civilizations or societies – close enough to meaningfully interact – are at or near the point where they are able to perform such large and expensive computations will have reached a point where will share technologies, only building one simulation, considering how large a computational undertaking it would be. Therefore, two or more simulations would occur when the simulated universe is large enough to contain non-interacting civilizations.

3. Using a similar assumption to the above, that a dependent collection of civilizations will likely only develop a single (or few) simulations, the occurrence of one simulation is unlikely to affect if another one is initiated.
4. This assumption follows approximately as it is unlikely two simulations are initiated at exactly the same moment, particularly if it is assumed that it is unlikely there are many simulation (i.e. λ is not too large).

Notably, I do not have to prove or even strongly argue for any assumption. The – previously discussed – point of this paper is not to argue that we positively do not live in a simulation but just that we do not necessarily live in a simulation. Hence assumptions do not have to be argued for absolutely. I just have to argue that they are *possible* with non-negligible probability.

B. Identical Distributions Assumption

The identical distributions assumption can be expressed as in Assumption 2.

Assumption 2. *Any civilization creates simulations with the exact same distribution as any other.*

The idea that distinct universes have the same distribution can be most succinctly argued for by noticing the argued use of the simulations: they are “ancestor” simulations. Worlds – or, as it may turn out, simulations – are simulating themselves. Hence, a simulation will roughly simulate – in time – themselves and they are simulations of the simulation above them. I.e., identity cascades down the layers of simulation, motivated by the fact societies want to perform relevant ancestor simulations.

III. DERIVATION OF A BOUND ON THE PROBABILITY OF LIVING IN A SIMULATION: A SIMPLIFIED MODEL

I first start with a simplified model, using a more simple model of simulation creation for a universe. This model is – in some ways – just a warm up to the more complex model that follows it but serves, in its own right, as a counter-example to the trilemma. To be clear, Assumption 1 presented earlier is – for Sec. III – relaxed to allow for a simpler initial analysis.

A. Simplified Model Setup

Consider a single base reality (i.e. a world/society/universe that is *not* in a simulation), I assume that this world/society/universe *including ones that are simulations at any “depth”* – and all other worlds/societies/universes – creates exactly one simulation with probability $q \in [0, 1]$. The only other option that this model allows is that *no* simulations are ever created. This happens with probability $1 - q$. This setup is what replaces Assumption 1 in this simplified model.

B. Probability any uniformly chosen world/society/universe is a simulation in this model

The first – and crucial – step in attempting to figure the probability we live in a simulation – using given assumptions – is to find the implied – by the assumptions – distribution of how many nested worlds there are in the model. This is accomplished in Lemma 1.

Lemma 1. *The probability that there are exactly $k \in \mathbb{N}$ nested worlds is:*

$$q^{k-1}(1-q), \quad (5)$$

where $q \in [0, 1]$ is the probability a simulation or based reality ever create a simulation of their own.

Proof. Let $\mathbb{P}[\geq j]$ denote the probability there are at least $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$ worlds in the model and $\mathbb{P}[\geq j \mid \geq k]$ there are at least $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$ worlds in the model given there are at least $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ worlds in the model. Then,

$$\mathbb{P}[\geq j+1 \mid \geq j] = q \quad (6)$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathbb{P}[\geq j+1] = \mathbb{P}[\geq j+1 \mid \geq j]\mathbb{P}[\geq j] = q\mathbb{P}[\geq j]. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, I can recursively calculate:

$$\mathbb{P}[\geq j+1] = q^j\mathbb{P}[\geq 1] = q^j. \quad (8)$$

Where I have used that there is definitely at least one world (base reality) in the model. This provides the result as: $\forall k \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\mathbb{P}[k] = \mathbb{P}[\geq k] - \mathbb{P}[\geq k+1] = q^{k-1} - q^k = q^{k-1}(1-q). \quad (9)$$

□

The next step is to establish how the probability of living in a simulation relates to the number of nested worlds in the model, as done in Lemma 2.

Lemma 2. *Assuming there are exactly k nested worlds, the probability of living in a simulation is $\frac{1}{k}$.*

Proof. Simulations are – at the basic level, from the inside – indistinguishable from reality; otherwise there is no point in performing them (it would taint the results). Hence, assuming there are $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ worlds, we can do no better than estimating the probability that we live in a simulation as $\frac{1}{k}$. □

Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 can be combined – in Theorem 1 – to give the probability we live in a simulation.

Theorem 1. *The probability we live in a simulation, according to the simplified model, is:*

$$1 - \frac{(q-1)}{q} \ln(1-q), \quad (10)$$

where q is the probability a simulation or based reality ever create a simulation of their own.

Proof. For convenience, denote the probability we live in a simulation by $Q \in [0, 1]$. Then, using Lemma 1:

$$Q = 1 - \sum_{z=1}^{\infty} \left(\mathbb{P}[\text{we do not live in a simulation} \mid z] \mathbb{P}[z] \right) \quad (11)$$

$$= 1 - \frac{(1-q)}{q} \sum_{z=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{z} q^z \right) = 1 - \frac{(q-1)}{q} \ln(1-q). \quad (12)$$

□

The values implied by the equation derived in Theorem 1 for the probability of living in a simulation for varying values of q are shown – for illustrative purposes – in Table I.

q	Q
0.9	0.7442
0.7	0.8662
0.5	0.3069

TABLE I. Values of Q for given values of q .

IV. DERIVATION OF A BOUND ON THE PROBABILITY OF LIVING IN A SIMULATION: A MORE COMPLEX MODEL

I now move onto the more complex and main model of how nested simulations may be structured in relation to each other. This model now allows for multiple simulations to be nested within a single world/simulation (but neither is nested in the other). This is a more complex model than the previous one. The analysis is therefore less direct and clear and first requires a preparatory lemma: Lemma 3. To aid in reading this section, a diagram showing the dependencies of all theorems, lemmas, and corollaries is provided in Appendix A.

Lemma 3. *Regardless of the offspring distribution used, if $G : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the probability generating function of that offspring distribution and $H : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the probability generating function of the total number of worlds in the tree: $\forall s \in \mathbb{N}$,*

$$H(s) = sG(H(s)). \quad (13)$$

Proof. A useful fact about Galton-Watson trees is their self-similarity: the distribution of the behavior of the entire tree is identical to the distribution of the behavior of the subtree below any specific node.

Therefore, if the top node of a tree, W , has $k \in \mathbb{N}$ children and each one – labeled $j \in \mathbb{N}^{\leq k}$ – is the top of a subtree, W_j , of size $|W_j|$, then:

$$|W| = 1 + \sum_{j=1}^k (|W_j|). \quad (14)$$

Letting $p_k \in [0, 1]$ be the probability that a single node has exactly $k \in \mathbb{N}$ immediate children. Then, $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, I use the

definition of probability generating functions, $H(s) = \mathbb{E}[s^{|W|}]$, and Eqn. 14 to derive:

$$H(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(p_k \mathbb{E}[s^{1+\sum_{j=1}^k |W_{j|}}] \right). \quad (15)$$

This can be further simplified by considering the aforementioned self-similarity to note that each $|W_{j|}$ is independent of all others. This then implies that:

$$\mathbb{E}[s^{1+\sum_{j=1}^k |W_{j|}}] = s \mathbb{E} \left[\prod_{j=1}^k s^{|W_{j|}} \right] = s \prod_{j=1}^k \mathbb{E}[s^{|W_{j|}}] = s(H(s))^k. \quad (16)$$

Therefore, Eqn. 15 can be simplified to:

$$H(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(p_k s(H(s))^k \right) = sG(H(s)). \quad (17)$$

□

I now pause to present – without proof – Theorem 2, a well-known theorem due to Lagrange that will prove useful later.

Theorem 2. *Lagrange inversion theorem [5]*

Let $A(s) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (a_j s^j)$ and $\Phi = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\phi_j s^j)$ be power series such that:

$$A(s) = s\Phi(A(s)). \quad (18)$$

Then, for any $R(s) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (r_j s^j)$, $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$n[x_n]R(A(x)) = [z^{n-1}]R'(z)\Phi^n(z), \quad (19)$$

where $[x^j] : F(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denotes the coefficient of the x^j term in the power series it acts on.

Returning to the main argument of the paper, Theorem 2 is immediately useful, in conjunction with Lemma 2 when used in the proof of Lemma 4.

Lemma 4. *The probability that there are $n \in \mathbb{N}$ total worlds is:*

$$e^{-\lambda n} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} n^{n-1}}{n!}. \quad (20)$$

Proof. Let $|W|$ denote the number of worlds. Using Lemma 3, $H(s)$ is implicitly defined by:

$$H(s) = sG(H(s)). \quad (21)$$

As the offspring distribution is assumed to be Poi_λ , G is the probability generating function of Poi_λ .

Eqn. 21 can be solved – for $H(s)$ – using the Lagrange inversion formula (Theorem 2), by setting $R(s) = s$: $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$n[x^n]H(x) = [z^{n-1}]G^n(z). \quad (22)$$

Therefore, as H is the probability generating function of the number of worlds, $|W|$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}[|W| = n] &= \frac{1}{n} [z^{n-1}]G^n(z) = \frac{1}{n} [z^{n-1}]e^{\lambda n(z-1)} \\ &= \frac{e^{-\lambda n}}{n} [z^{n-1}] \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda^j n^j z^j}{j!} \right) = e^{-\lambda n} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} n^{n-1}}{n!}, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where the second equality follows from the fact that G is the probability generating function of Poi_λ . □

With Lemma 4 complete, we are now ready to prove the main result of this paper: Theorem 3.

Theorem 3. *Assuming the model laid out in Sec. IV, the probability we live in a simulation is:*

$$1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(e^{-\lambda n} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} n^{n-2}}{n!} \right). \quad (24)$$

Proof. Lemma 2 argues that, assuming $|W| = n$, the probability we live in a simulation is $1/n$. Therefore, additionally using Lemma 4:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}[\text{We do not live in a simulation}] &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n} \mathbb{P}[|W| = n] \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(e^{-\lambda n} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} n^{n-2}}{n!} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Therefore, the probability that we live in a simulation is:

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{We live in a simulation}] = 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(e^{-\lambda n} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} n^{n-2}}{n!} \right). \quad (26)$$

□

Corollary 1. *The probability we live in a simulation can be bounded as:*

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{We live in a simulation}] \leq 1 - e^{-\lambda} - \lambda e^{-2\lambda}. \quad (27)$$

Proof. Using Theorem 3:

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{We live in a simulation}] = 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(e^{-\lambda n} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} n^{n-2}}{n!} \right). \quad (28)$$

As all terms in the summation – in Eqn. 28 – are positive:

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{We live in a simulation}] \leq 1 - e^{-\lambda} - \frac{\lambda e^{-2\lambda}}{2}. \quad (29)$$

□

V. EXAMPLE VALUES OF λ AND RESULTING PROBABILITIES

Again using Q to denote the probability we live in a simulation, in this section I give example bounds on Q according to the formula:

$$Q \leq 1 - e^{-\lambda} - \frac{\lambda e^{-2\lambda}}{2}. \quad (30)$$

A. Test Case: $\lambda = 0$

Set $\lambda = 0$, in Eqn. 27 then:

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{We live in a simulation}] \leq 1 - e^0 - 0e^0 = 0. \quad (31)$$

As should be expected.

B. More Plausible and Interesting Values of λ

I now use the above results to calculate example values of the probability we live in a simulation for a sample of values of λ . These values are displayed in Table II. These values are

λ	Upper bound on Q
1.5	0.7395
1.3	0.6792
1.1	0.6062
0.9	0.5190
0.7	0.4171
0.5	0.3015

TABLE II. Upper bound on Q for given values of λ .

what the argument that the trilemma from Ref. [1] is violated is based on.

VI. DISCUSSION

In this paper I have presented two models of how simulations could *possibly* be nested in each other and the accompanying probability distributions of how many simulations worlds/simulations build. Both of these models assumed that civilizations *did* create simulations with non-negligible probability and yet resulted in probabilities that we live in a simulation of much less than one.

This stands in stark contrast to the usual narrative we are given and arguably falsifies the trilemma presented before (from Ref. [1]). I return to this trilemma and reiterate how this model does not obey any of the given propositions:

1. “Almost no civilization reaches a level of technological maturity capable of running ancestor simulations”: A Poisson distribution with $\lambda \gg 0$ clearly does not set the probability of civilizations reaching technological maturity capable of running ancestor simulations to be negligibly small.
2. “Almost no civilization capable of running ancestor simulations chooses to do so”: Same as above.
3. “We are almost certainly living in a simulation”: The values of Table II clearly show this not to be the case.

I now turn to the limitations of the model. Assuming the distribution of simulations in a real or simulated universe is a Poisson distribution is perhaps questionable, as discussed in Sec. II A, but again, the point is to produce a *plausible* model – to introduce doubt – so I believe this is forgivable.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

This work was supported by the Quantum Advantage Pathfinder (EP/X026167/1).

Appendix A: Diagram of Dependence in Sec. IV

Fig. 1 is the promised diagram of the dependence of all lemmas, theorems, and corollaries in Sec. IV on each other.

-
- [1] N. Bostrom, *Philosophical Quarterly* **53**, 243 (2003).
 - [2] S. R. Beane, Z. Davoudi, and M. J. Savage, *The European Physical Journal A* **50** (2014).
 - [3] T. Campbell, H. Owahdi, J. Sauvageau, and D. Watkinson, *International Journal of Quantum Foundations* **3**, 78 (2017).
 - [4] M. M. Vopson, *AIP Advances* **13**, 105308 (2023).
 - [5] E. Surya and L. Warnke, *The American Mathematical Monthly* **130**, 944–948 (2023).

FIG. 1. Diagram of Sec. IV dependence